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TR72 BÖLGESİNİN DİŞ TİCARET YAPISI ANALİZİ

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ÖZ

Bir bölgedeki ticaret dinamikleri, ekonomik büyümenin şekillenmesinde belirleyici bir rol oynamaktadır. Piyasalara erişimin kolaylaştırılması, yenilikçiliğin teşvik edilmesi ve yatırımların bölgeye çekilmesi gibi unsurlar, sürdürülebilir kalkınmayı destekleyen temel etkenlerdendir. Bu çalışma, Türkiye'nin Kayseri, Yozgat ve Sivas illerini kapsayan TR72 bölgesine odaklanmakta ve 2013–2023 yılları arasındaki dış ticaret yapısını endüstri-içi ticaret (EİT) perspektifinden incelemektedir. Teknolojik sınıflandırmada Uluslararası Standart Sanayi Sınıflaması (ISIC) esas alınmış; EİT analizinde ise literatürde yaygın olarak kullanılan Grubel-Lloyd endeksi kullanılmıştır. Çalışma, bölgenin sektörel ticaret akışlarını ayrıntılı bir şekilde değerlendirmektedir.

Elde edilen bulgular, iller arasında dış ticaret performansında belirgin farklılıklar olduğunu göstermektedir. Kayseri, Serbest Ticaret Bölgesi'nin sağladığı avantajlarla küresel pazarlara yüksek düzeyde entegre olmuş durumdadır. Buna karşın, Yozgat ve Sivas'ta dış ticaretin daha çok tek yönlü yapıda ilerlediği ve endüstri-içi ticaret seviyesinin görece düşük olduğu gözlemlenmiştir. Bu durum, bölgesel kalkınmanın dengelenmesi adına hedefe yönelik politikaların uygulanması gerektiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Özellikle Sivas'taki Nuri Demirağ Organize Sanayi Bölgesi gibi alanlarda altyapının güçlendirilmesi ve bölgeye özgü dış ticaret teşviklerinin sunulması, bölgesel rekabetçiliği artırabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dış Ticaret, TR72, Endüstri içi ticaret, ISIC Sınıflandırma, Grubel-Lloyd

Jel Kodu: L60, M00, M16, M2

AN ANALYSIS OF THE FOREIGN TRADE STRUCTURE OF THE TR72 REGION⁴

ABSTRACT

The trade dynamics within a region play a critical role in shaping its economic growth by facilitating market access, fostering innovation, and attracting investments, driving therefore sustainable development. This study focuses on the TR72 region of Türkiye, which comprises the provinces of Kayseri, Yozgat, and Sivas, and examines its foreign trade structure also through the lens of intra-industry trade (IIT) over the period 2013–2023. Employing the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) for technological categorization and utilizing the Grubel-Lloyd index, one of the most widely applied methods for IIT analysis, the study provides a detailed sectoral examination of trade flows in the region.

The findings highlight significant variation in trade performance among the provinces. Kayseri demonstrates a strong integration into global markets, supported in part by the operational advantages offered by its Free Trade Zone. In contrast, Yozgat and Sivas tend to one-way trade, indicating relatively low levels of intra-industry trade, which suggests a need for targeted policy interventions. Improving industrial infrastructure and introducing region-specific trade incentives, particularly in designated areas such as the Nuri Demirağ Organized Industrial Zone in Sivas, could enhance competitiveness and promote balanced regional development.

Keywords: Foreign Trade, TR72, Intra-industry trade, ISIC Classification, Grubel-Lloyd

Jel Codes: L60, M00, M16, M2

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1. INTRODUCTION

International trade, the exchange of goods and services across different countries, plays a vital role in enhancing global economic interaction and, therefore, driving development worldwide. Since the emergence of classical international trade theories, such as Adam Smith's theory of absolute advantage and David Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage, economists have established a foundational framework for explaining why countries engage in trade and how they derive mutual benefits from it. According to Smith (1776), nations should focus on producing and trading goods in which they hold an absolute advantage, which means specializing in those goods that they can make more efficiently than others. Building on this foundation, Ricardo (1817) introduced the theory of comparative advantage, demonstrating that even countries lacking absolute efficiency can still gain from trade by specializing in goods they produce at a lower opportunity cost. Building upon these classical insights, the Heckscher-Ohlin theory posits that countries will export goods that intensively utilize their abundant production factors while importing those that rely on relatively scarce resources.

Importantly, the core principles of these trade theories are not confined to national economies; they are equally applicable to subnational regions, such as provinces or local areas, which can similarly benefit from specialization and trade. In this context, foreign trade plays a crucial role in influencing the economic growth of a region as it enhances regional development by increasing production capacity, improving competitiveness, and boosting employment. Moreover, the new markets and investment opportunities enabled by foreign trade allow regions to utilize their resources more efficiently, adopting more innovative approaches and advanced technologies. That's why foreign trade is considered an essential driving force for the sustainability and diversification of a region's economic development.

In recent decades, Intra-Industry Trade (IIT) analysis has become one of the most common methodologies for better understanding the trade dynamics of a specific region or nation. IIT highlights the level of exchange of similar products within the same industry or the level of export and import of similar products within the same sector. Therefore, analyzing the foreign trade structure of a region through the IIT analysis enables us to understand how regions increase their competitive advantage, their level of specialization, and open their markets to the global arena by fostering innovation.

Within this framework, the present study aims to provide practical insights for policymakers and various stakeholders in the TR72 region, one of Türkiye's 26 statistical regions, by examining its foreign trade structure. The analysis covers the provinces of Kayseri, Yozgat, and Sivas over the period 2013-2023. Additionally, this study aims to measure the intra-industry trade (IIT) level at the industry level within the TR72 region and its provinces by employing the Grubel-Lloyd Index, a widely recognized tool for measuring IIT, to assess trade patterns across the region and its provinces over the past decade.

The methodology of this study involves calculating Intra-industry trade (IIT) indices for various sectors in the TR72 region. These sectors are classified by factor intensity, following the ISIC Rev. 3 technological classification. Data for this analysis is sourced from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK). By examining the structure of IIT across these sectors, the study aims to provide deeper insight into the region's level of trade integration and its patterns of economic specialization.

The paper is organized into several key sections. The first section presents a literature review, focusing on studies that have analyzed foreign trade through the lens of IIT. The second section offers a socio-economic overview of the TR72 region and its constituent provinces, Kayseri, Sivas, and Yozgat. It highlights demographic characteristics, labor force dynamics, and regional competitiveness. The third section examines the foreign trade profile of the region, summarizing key data on exports and imports, highlighting the most commonly exported and imported goods, and identifying the main trading partners from both export and import perspectives. This background serves as a foundation for the detailed IIT analysis that follows. The fourth section forms the core of the study, employing the Grubel-Lloyd index to quantify the level of Intra-industry trade within the TR72 region and its provinces, based on the ISIC

Rev. 3 classification. This analysis identifies the sectors where significant levels of IIT are observed. The paper concludes by summarizing key findings and providing policy recommendations to enhance the region's trade performance and economic integration.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides a review of the literature on foreign trade analysis, with a particular emphasis on the primary studies that have examined Intra-industry trade involving Türkiye using the Grubel-Lloyd method, focusing on specific industries. The literature is organized chronologically to reflect the progression of research over time and grouped according to country groups, concluding with an example of a paper that has applied this type of analysis not only at the national level but also at the regional level.

Mainly, researchers analyze the IIT performance of Türkiye, comparing it with that of different EU countries. For instance, Küçükahmetoğlu (2002) examines Türkiye's Intra-industry trade with the European Union (EU) from 1989 to 1998, utilizing the Grubel-Lloyd index for analysis. It collects trade data categorized by product groups according to the SITC Rev. 3 classification, with a focus on standard, intermediate, and high-technology goods. The results indicate that while Türkiye's average levels of Intra-industry trade were initially low compared to those of any EU country, they showed a positive trend, particularly for standard technology goods, highlighting a significant relationship with real income growth and economic integration.

Also, Altay and Şen (2009) perform a comparative analysis of Türkiye's Intra-industry trade performance in the European Union (15) market from 1995 to 2007. Utilizing methodologies such as the Export Similarity Index, Grubel-Lloyd Index, and Brühlhart Index, the study analyzed Euro-based export and import data for Türkiye and selected rival countries. The results indicated that Türkiye's Intra-industry trade performance was higher than that of its competitors in the EU (15) during the specified period.

Later, Erün (2010) also conducted a study analyzing Intra-industry trade (IIT) between Türkiye and the European Union in the food and live animal sectors, as well as their sub-sectors. Utilizing a quantitative methodology, the research examined trade data from Türkiye and various EU member countries, with a focus on the years preceding 2010. The findings indicated that Türkiye primarily engages in high-quality vertical IIT with the EU, while the trade with individual European countries tends to reflect low-quality vertical IIT. This suggests a trade pattern where Türkiye exports lower-quality goods to developed nations, aligning with the characteristics of vertical IIT.

Additionally, Kuşat (2020) conducted a study analyzing Intra-industry trade in the fisheries sector between Türkiye and the EU-28 countries using the Grubel-Lloyd Index. The research utilized trade data from the United Nations database, covering the period from 2009 to 2019. The findings indicated that Intra-industry trade between Türkiye and the EU 28 was minimal, highlighting Türkiye's sectoral superiority in this one-way trade.

Saygın (2020) examines the Intra-industry trade (IIT) levels between Türkiye and selected EU countries in the iron and steel sector. The methodology involves the Grubel-Lloyd index to analyze trade patterns. The data used spans from 2009 to 2019, focusing on Türkiye and various EU nations. The results indicate a significant increase in IIT levels, highlighting the evolving trade dynamics and product differentiation in the sector during the specified period.

The study by Sezer and Masca (2021) analyzes Intra-industry trade (IIT) in the Turkish manufacturing sector with selected EU countries from 2000 to 2020, utilizing the Grubel-Lloyd index as the primary methodology. The research focuses on trade data from the Turkish Statistical Institute for 18 European countries. The findings indicate that Türkiye's Intra-industry trade is predominantly high in

product groups with low added value, with significant trade levels observed particularly with the UK, Germany, France, Poland, Bulgaria, and Romania.

Other scholars have investigated IIT, comparing Türkiye with country groups different from the EU, or examining the IIT phenomenon in relation to a specific sector, or analyzing IIT trends within regional case studies.

For instance, Şahin (2016a) analyzes Türkiye's furniture industry in foreign trade from 2000 to 2015. The results of the Grubel-Lloyd Index for Intra-industry trade and the Revealed Comparative Advantage Index for competitiveness show that the industry engages in low-quality vertical Intra-industry trade. Competitiveness in the furniture sector has steadily increased over the period analyzed. Additionally, Şahin (2016b) examines the foreign trade structure of the fresh fruit and vegetable sector in Türkiye and the BRIC countries (Brazil, Russia, India, and China) from 2000 to 2014. Using Intra-industry trade (IIT) analysis and a competitiveness evaluation, the study finds that IIT in this sector is low for both Türkiye and BRIC countries. However, Türkiye is highly competitive, while the BRIC countries are less competitive in the fresh fruit and vegetable sector.

Ersen (2020) analyzes Intra-industry trade (IIT) in the paper pulp, paper, and paperboard machines sector between Türkiye and Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries from 2009 to 2018. Using the Grubel-Lloyd and Brühlhart (A and B) indices for HS 8439 and HS 8441 product codes, the study finds that Türkiye's trade is primarily inter-industry. While seven CEE countries showed IIT values exceeding 0.5 for HS 8439 and six for HS 8441, the Czech Republic had the highest IIT, with Türkiye and Ukraine showing the lowest values; the trade patterns varied by product group and period.

Doru and Özer (2022) employ econometric analysis to investigate the determinants of Intra-industry trade (IIT) in the automotive sector between Türkiye and 24 OECD member countries. Utilizing panel data from 2003 to 2019, the research applies the Grubel-Lloyd index to measure IIT levels. Key findings indicate that factors such as development level, market size dissimilarity, economies of scale, and product differentiation significantly influence IIT. The results suggest that enhancing these factors could increase Türkiye's share of Intra-industry trade in the automotive sector.

After Saygın (2020), Ergün (2023) also analyzed Intra-industry trade in the iron and steel sector, but with a different country group: the Black Sea Economic Cooperation (BSEC) countries. Using the Grubel-Lloyd index, the study covered the period from 2018 to 2022 and utilized data from BSEC member countries. The results indicated that the intensity of Intra-industry trade for Türkiye in this sector was not at the desired level compared to the number of member countries, highlighting challenges in achieving optimal trade integration within the region. Therefore, the research highlights the importance of imports for production and exports for value generation.

Aydemir (2024) conducts an analysis of Intra-industry trade (IIT) in Türkiye's aquaculture sector using the Grubel-Lloyd index. The study examines trade data from 2010 to 2022, focusing on four and 6-digit HS-coded product groups. The analysis reveals a low level of IIT in Türkiye's fishery trade, characterized by an export-oriented structure, particularly in raw seafood products. In contrast, processed seafood shows an import-oriented pattern. The findings suggest that enhancing trade relationships with high-income countries could improve Türkiye's performance in the aquaculture sector.

In 2024, Aydemir also analyzes Intra-industry trade (IIT) in Türkiye's forest products sector using the Grubel-Lloyd index, which measures the extent of trade in similar product groups. The research utilizes 3-digit foreign trade data from the Standard International Trade Classification (SITC) for the period 2010-2022, with a focus on wood and paper products. The findings indicate that while Türkiye's forest products sector transitioned from a trade deficit to a surplus since 2018, the IIT values remained low (0.33, 0.47) throughout the period, with wood products showing higher IIT levels before 2018 and lower thereafter. The study highlights that the trade is predominantly inter-industry, with a notable export

orientation due to the surplus in foreign trade.

In relation to regional analysis, Şahin (2017) examines the role of foreign trade in the development of regions, rather than nations, with a specific focus on TR81. This Level 2 region encompasses the provinces of Zonguldak, Karabük, and Bartın. The study first examines the region's foreign trade structure and then analyzes its intra-industry trade (IIT) using the Grubel-Lloyd method. The findings suggest that Zonguldak leads TR81's foreign trade, with key exports to countries such as Romania and imports from Ukraine, primarily concentrated in scale-intensive industries. However, the overall level of intra-industry trade in the TR81 region remains low.

Indeed, this study aims to assess the foreign trade structure of the TR72 region, with a particular focus on measuring intra-industry trade (IIT) levels across all industries and provinces, including Kayseri, Yozgat, and Sivas, over the period 2013-2023. The analysis employs the widely used Grubel-Lloyd index and applies the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) to categorize industries by technological intensity. Due to the use of 2-digit level data, a more detailed classification of IIT into vertical and horizontal components, such as that offered by the Abdulrahman (1991) method, is not feasible. Instead, the study provides a comprehensive sectoral overview of trade flows in the region, highlighting significant variations in trade performance. The study begins by highlighting the primary socio-economic characteristics of the TR72 region.

3. SOCIO-ECONOMIC OVERVIEW OF THE TR72 REGION

The TR72 Region is one of the 26 statistical sub-regions of Türkiye. The TR72 region, situated in the Central Anatolia Area, comprises the provinces of Kayseri, Sivas, and Yozgat. With a surface area of 59,528 km², the region constitutes 7.60% of Türkiye's surface area. Using data available on the TUIK portal and reorganized by the authors of this paper, this part of the research aims to shape the socio-economic landscape of the TR72 region and its provinces. Table 1 shows the population potential of the TR72 Region. As seen in Table 1, despite fluctuations in individual region populations, the ratio of the TR72 region's population to Türkiye's total population remains relatively stable, ranging between 2.8% and 3.2% throughout the years. There is a notable increase in the population of Sivas and Yozgat in 2023 compared to previous years. This is potentially because this region is one of the closest and safest areas to the zone that was impacted by the February 2023 earthquake (i.e., migration from the Kahramanmaraş earthquake zone).

Table 1. Population Potential of the TR72 Region

Years	Kayseri	Sivas	Yozgat	TR72	Türkiye	TR72/Türkiye
2013	1.295.355	439.564	264.470	1.999.389	70.034.413	2,85%
2014	1.322.376	446.663	265.792	2.034.831	71.286.182	2,85%
2015	1.341.056	451.930	262.864	2.055.850	72.523.134	2,83%
2016	1.358.980	458.656	268.324	2.085.960	73.671.748	2,83%
2017	1.376.722	464.455	269.334	2.110.511	74.761.132	2,82%
2018	1.389.680	470.589	270.658	2.130.927	75.666.497	2,82%
2019	1.407.409	475.643	275.026	2.158.078	77.151.280	2,80%
2020	1.421.455	477.931	275.935	2.175.321	77.736.041	2,80%
2021	1.434.357	482.978	277.041	2.194.376	78.908.631	2,78%

2022	1.441.523	485.991	276.545	2.204.059	79.613.279	2,77%
2023	1.445.683	650.401	420.699	2.516.783	79.399.292	3,17%

Table 2 shows a general decline in the labor force participation rate from 2013 to 2020, followed by a slight increase in 2021, 2022, and 2023. This suggests that the COVID-19 pandemic was crucial in causing significant changes in workforce dynamics and economic conditions. The employment rate exhibits instability, with a notable decline during 2019 and 2020, followed by a substantial improvement starting from 2021. This indicates both challenges in maintaining employment levels within the TR72 Region and a positive response of the labor market in the period following the first two years of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, there's a notable increase in 2022 and 2023, potentially indicating efforts to boost employment opportunities.

Table 2. Labor Force Status of the TR72 Region

Indicators	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Unemployment Rate (%)	9,6	9,6	9,7	8,4	11,9	13,2	14,5	12,8	11,7	9,4	9,2
Labor Force Participation Rate (%)	50,7	47,9	48,9	49,6	49,4	47,9	47,5	44,9	48,4	50	50,7
Employment Rate (%)	45,8	43,3	44,2	45,4	43,5	41,6	40,6	39,2	42,8	45,3	46,1

The URAK (Regional Development Index) reflects the overall development and competitiveness of regions. Therefore, it is a valuable tool for assessing the competitiveness of regions within Türkiye. Unfortunately, the most up-to-date data dates back to 2018. This index evaluates various sub-components to provide a comprehensive overview of regional performance. The URAK sub-components include Human Capital, Innovation, Production and Trade, and Livability, which are critical for understanding a region's economic health and potential.

Regarding the Overall Index, the higher the index, the better the economic situation. The first part of Table 3 reports the Overall Index Ranking. For instance, Kayseri, with an overall score of 17.94, is the highest-ranked province in the TR72 region. This indicates a relatively strong competitive position compared to its regional peers. Sivas, scoring 13.9, holds a moderate position in the overall competitiveness ranking. Indeed, Yozgat, with a score of 12.68, is the lowest-ranked among the three provinces, indicating challenges in competitiveness.

Regarding the sub-component Analysis, reported in the second section of Table 3, both Kayseri and Sivas show a significant investment in human capital, which reflects the local educational infrastructure and workforce capabilities. Indeed, Yozgat's lower ranking indicates room for improvement in educational outcomes and workforce development. Regarding the Innovation Sub-component, once again, Kayseri is the best-performing province, excelling in innovation, which suggests a strong presence of R&D activities and a conducive environment for technological advancements. Unfortunately, both Sivas and Yozgat lag in innovation, highlighting the need for policies that foster innovation ecosystems and support for startups. The third sub-component, represented by Production and Trade, shows that Kayseri's production and trade metrics are relatively robust, underpinned by a diverse industrial base and strong trade links.

On the other hand, data related to both Sivas and Yozgat indicate that both provinces face significant challenges in production and trade, necessitating strategies to enhance industrial productivity and market access. Finally, regarding the Livability sub-component, Kayseri scores well in terms of livability, which encompasses factors such as quality of life, infrastructure, and public services. Once

again, the scores for both Sivas and Yozgat reflect the need for improvements in living conditions and

Year	Kayseri		2016-2017 Overall Index Ranking		Yozgat		Türkiye	
	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
2013	1.331.003.504	1.278.983.408	57.372.481	88.047.920	19.611.871	7.163.909	1.407.987.856	1.374.194.337
2014	1.420.770.479	1.285.187.162	68.883.024	40.003.472	12.887.246	11.202.933	1.502.540.749	1.336.393.567
2015	1.426.622.761	1.331.234.647	70.198.498	54.462.740	13.053.771	13.281.544	1.510.775.033	1.398.978.940
2016	1.380.004.802	1.314.637.792	72.396.149	62.722.409	19.273.804	29.198.350	1.471.674.755	1.406.558.551
2017	1.454.452.269	1.610.951.152	81.877.888	52.029.512	11.385.395	28.828.553	1.547.715.552	1.691.209.217

Competitiveness Index by Sub-Components in TR72 Region		Human Capital	Innovation	Production and Trade	Livability
Kayseri		39	9	27	16
Sivas		30	31	59	39
Yozgat		52	39	53	49

infrastructure to attract and retain talent.

Table 3. Competitiveness Index Ranking of the TR72 Region

In brief, Kayseri's high rankings across most sub-components underscore its position as a regional leader, driven by substantial human capital, innovation, and livability. Conversely, Sivas and Yozgat require targeted interventions to boost their competitiveness, particularly in innovation, production, and trade.

4. FOREIGN TRADE WITHIN THE TR72 REGION

In Tables 4 and 5, the foreign trade structure of the TR72 Region is analyzed. As of 2013, Table 4 shows that the TR72 region conducted exports worth € 1,407,987,856 and imports worth € 1,374,194,337. By 2023, exports increased to € 3,084,778,843, while imports also registered an increase, albeit a minor one, reaching € 1,917,509,885. While exports over 10 years increased by about 220%, imports increased by only 140%.

Table 4. Foreign Trade Volume of Provinces in the TR72 Region

2018	1.770.017.136	1.184.682.300	81.551.741	46.636.007	6.507.009	20.276.399	1.858.075.886	1.251.594.706
2019	1.980.044.313	1.075.530.597	82.890.460	43.238.616	12.085.574	20.902.663	2.075.020.347	1.139.671.876
2020	1.998.121.654	1.102.647.463	80.199.330	34.345.461	13.372.374	21.265.210	2.091.693.358	1.158.258.134
2021	2.728.606.346	1.553.584.745	70.996.995	46.465.903	14.993.953	13.202.092	2.814.597.294	1.613.252.740
2022	3.300.533.069	1.781.698.720	99.713.077	42.047.045	55.211.499	37.789.963	3.455.457.645	1.861.535.728
2023	2.972.547.076	1.786.624.160	92.941.239	82.377.996	19.290.528	48.507.729	3.084.778.843	1.917.509.885

Table 5 presents the shares of the individual provinces within the TR72 region, which are reported separately for each province according to its share in Figures 1, 2, and 3.

Table 5: % Share of Provinces in the TR72 Region in Regional Trade

Year	Kayseri		Sivas		Yozgat	
	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
2013	94,53%	93,07%	4,07%	6,41%	1,39%	0,52%
2014	94,56%	96,17%	4,58%	2,99%	0,86%	0,84%
2015	94,43%	95,16%	4,65%	3,89%	0,92%	0,95%
2016	93,77%	93,46%	4,92%	4,46%	1,31%	2,08%
2017	93,97%	95,25%	5,29%	3,08%	0,74%	1,67%
2018	95,26%	94,65%	4,39%	3,73%	0,35%	1,62%
2019	95,42%	94,37%	3,99%	3,79%	0,58%	1,83%
2020	95,53%	95,20%	3,83%	2,97%	0,64%	1,84%
2021	96,94%	96,30%	2,52%	2,88%	0,53%	0,82%
2022	95,52%	95,71%	2,89%	2,26%	1,60%	2,03%
2023	96,36%	93,17%	3,01%	4,30%	0,63%	2,53%

As shown in Figure 1, Kayseri consistently dominates both exports and imports in the TR72 region, maintaining, respectively, over 94% of the total exports and 93% of the total imports in the TR72 region throughout the period.

Figure 1. Kayseri's % Share in the regional trade within the TR72 Region

Figure 2 shows Sivas' shares of exports and imports. Sivas represents the second-largest share in regional trade, yet it is significantly smaller than Kayseri. Indeed, both exports and imports' share of Sivas registered critical levels of volatility. Sivas' export shares ranged from a low of 2.52% in 2021 to a high of 5.29% in 2017; Sivas' imports fluctuated more compared to Kayseri, which currently enjoys a more stable trading structure.

Figure 2. Sivas % Share in the regional trade within the TR72 Region

Yozgat holds the smallest share in both exports and imports. As shown in Figure 3, the export share was lowest in 2018 at 0.35% and highest in 2022 at 1.60%. The import share varied more widely, from 0.52% in 2013 to 2.53% in 2023.

Figure 3. Yozgat % Share in the regional trade within the TR72 Region

Table 6 summarizes the primary trade partners of TR72 for exports and imports from 2013 to

2023. For exports, Germany, Iraq, and the Kayseri Free Zone consistently appear as key partners, with notable contributions from the USA, Italy, and other countries. For imports, the Russian Fed, the Republic of China, and Kazakhstan cover the most considerable portion, indicating their significant roles as suppliers. The recurring presence of specific regions reflects established trade relationships and economic dependencies that have persisted over the decade.

Table 6: Top 5 Countries with the highest Exports and Imports for the TR72 Region

Year	Export	Import
2013	Iraq, Germany, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, Libya, USA	Russian Fed., Kazakhstan, Rep. of China, Germany, Uzbekistan
2014	Iraq, Germany, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, USA, Turkmenistan	Spain, Russian Fed., Kazakhstan, Rep. of China, Germany
2015	Iraq, Germany, USA, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, Turkmenistan	Rep. of China, Spain, Kazakhstan, Russian Fed., Uzbekistan
2016	Iraq, Germany, USA, Algeria, Kayseri Free Zone Trade	Rep. of China, Russian Fed., Kazakhstan, South Korea Kayseri Free Trade Zone*, Germany
2017	Iraq, Germany, Italy, Belgium, USA, Kayseri Free Zone Trade	Spain, Russian Fed., Rep. of China, Kazakhstan, Thailand
2018	Iraq, Germany, Italy, Belgium, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, Algeria	Russian Fed., Spain, Rep. of China, Uzbekistan, Polonia
2019	Germany, Italy, Iraq, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, USA, UK, Israel	Russian Fed., Rep. of China, Uzbekistan, Polonia, USA
2020	Iraq, Germany, USA, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, Italy, UK	Russian Fed., Rep. of China, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, South Korea
2021	Iraq, Germany, USA, Italy, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, Israel	Rep. of China, Russian Fed., South Korea, Uzbekistan, Germany
2022	Germany, Iraq, USA, Italy, Kayseri Free Zone Trade, Israel	Rep. of China, Russian Fed., South Korea, USA, Malaysia
2023	Germany, Iraq, Australia, USA, Italy	Russian Fed., Rep. of China, South Korea, USA, Germany

Table 7 outlines the top exporting destinations by value in Euros for Kayseri, Sivas, and Yozgat from 2013 to 2023. For Kayseri, Iraq consistently leads as the primary export destination, with export values reaching a peak in 2022. Sivas mainly exports to the Republic of China, though the USA has emerged as a significant partner in recent years. This trend indicates strong and stable trade relations with these countries. Yozgat's export destinations are more varied, with Iraq dominating the early years, followed by the UK, the Netherlands, Ukraine, and Germany in subsequent years.

Table 7: The Top Exporting Countries (in Euros) for the Provinces in the TR72 Region

Year	Kayseri		Sivas		Yozgat	
	Country	Value (Euro)	Country	Value (Euro)	Country	Value (Euro)

2013	Iraq	195.098.169	Rep. of China	18.860.904	Iraq	3.417.642
2014	Iraq	199.712.275	Rep. of China	15.171.322	Iraq	3.427.410
2015	Iraq	207.145.539	Rep. of China	13.778.924	Iraq	1.898.189
2016	Iraq	239.820.017	Rep. of China	17.043.473	Iraq	2.537.791
2017	Iraq	209.268.054	Rep. of China	12.698.002	Iraq	3.964.840
2018	Iraq	221.916.156	Rep. of China	9.963.426	Iraq	3.389.850
2019	Iraq	302.668.733	Rep. of China	11.951.011	UK	40.066.450
2020	Iraq	255.550.764	Rep. of China	11.506.313	UK	4.708.788
2021	Iraq	221.916.156	USA	9.963.426	Netherland	3.389.850
2022	Germany	302.668.733	USA	11.951.011	Ukraine	40.066.450
2023	Iraq	255.550.764	USA	11.506.313	Germany	4.708.788

Table 8 reveals the primary import partners for Kayseri, Sivas, and Yozgat from 2013 to 2023. For Kayseri, the Russian Fed and the Republic of China dominate, with significant import values recorded in recent years. Sivas exhibits a varied pattern, with top partners including Romania, the Russian Federation, Germany, and the Republic of China. Yozgat primarily imports from the Republic of China and Germany, with notable peaks in 2016 and 2023. The diverse sourcing of imports across different regions indicates strategic international trade relations.

Table 8: The Top Importing Countries (in Euros) for the Provinces in the TR72 Region

Year	Kayseri		Sivas		Yozgat	
	Country	Value (Euro)	Country	Value (Euro)	Country	Value (Euro)
2013	Russian Fed.	164.274.270	Romania	23.025.581	Rep. of China	1.189.687
2014	Spain	153.894.598	Russian Fed.	9.517.970	Rep. of China	1.485.603
2015	Rep. of China	175.585.500	Russian Fed.	10.626.098	Germany	3.335.055
2016	Rep. of China	295.988.318	Germany	14.015.627	Germany	13.124.351
2017	Spain	278.842.423	Saudi Arabia	19.133.222	Germany	10.556.431
2018	Russian Fed.	166.136.181	Russian Fed.	13.364.313	Rep. of China	4.639.614
2019	Russian Fed.	155.402.724	Russian Fed.	11.149.041	Germany	6.663.533
2020	Russian Fed.	165.110.373	Rep. of China	7.573.159	Germany	8.730.144
2021	Rep. of China	248.888.137	Rep. of China	14.222.434	Italy	3.131.424
2022	Rep. of China	323.538.011	Rep. of China	12.781.470	Netherlands	3.046.838

2023	Russian Fed.	412.884.674	Rep. of China	18.250.166	Rep. of China	15.927.260
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Table 9 presents the most exported and imported products in the TR72 region, categorized by their ISIC Rev. 3 2-digit classifications (see Appendix 1), from 2013 to 2022. The primary exported products consist of categories 27 (Basic metals), 28 (Fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment), 29 (Machinery and equipment n.e.c. (not elsewhere classified)), and 36 (Furniture; manufacturing n.e.c.), while imports frequently include categories 1 (agriculture, hunting, and related service activities), 24 (Chemicals and chemical products), 27 (Basic metals), and 29 (Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.). This indicates stable trade patterns with specific industrial sectors dominating both exports and imports.

Table 9: Top 5 Products Exported and Imported by the TR72 Region

Year	Most Exported Products	Most Imported Products
2013		1, 17, 24, 27, 29
2014-2015		1, 24, 27, 29, 35
2016	17, 27, 28, 29, 36	1, 24, 27, 29, 32
2017		1, 24, 27, 29, 35
2018-2019		1, 17, 24, 27, 29
2020	27, 28, 29, 31, 36	1, 24, 27, 29, 31
2021-2022		1, 17, 24, 27, 29
2023		

Table 10 illustrates the top 5 exported products across provinces in the TR72 region from 2013 to 2023. The data highlights consistent trends and fluctuations in import preferences among Kayseri, Sivas, and Yozgat, reflecting evolving economic dynamics and trade patterns within the region. For Kayseri, the most exported products include 17 (textiles), 27 (basic metals), 28 (Fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment), and 31 (Electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c). Sivas’ exports primarily consist of textiles (14), metals (15), and chemicals (26). In Yozgat, the main exported items are textiles (15 and 18), metals (28), and machinery (29).

Table 10: Top 5 Products Exported by Provinces in the TR72 Region

Year	Kayseri	Sivas	Yozgat
2013		14, 15, 26, 28, 29	15, 18, 28, 29, 33
2014		14, 15, 26, 29, 36	1, 15, 18, 25, 28
2015	17, 28, 29, 31, 36	14, 15, 26, 29, 33	15, 18, 28, 32, 33
2016		14, 15, 26, 29, 36	15, 18, 19, 21, 28
2017		14, 15, 24, 26, 29	15, 21, 24, 25, 33
2018		14, 15, 24, 26, 29	15, 17, 18, 33, 34
2019		14, 15, 24, 26, 29	1, 15, 18, 29, 34
2020	17, 27, 28, 29, 36	14, 15, 24, 26, 29	1, 15, 18, 20, 29
2021		14, 24, 26, 29, 33	1, 15, 20, 26, 29
2022		24, 26, 29, 33, 36	17, 18, 25, 26, 29
2023	27, 28, 29, 31, 36	24, 26, 28, 29, 33	15, 18, 20, 28, 29

As shown in Table 11, Kayseri's imports are dominated by sectors 1 (Agriculture, hunting, and related service activities), 24 (Chemicals and chemical products), 27 (Basic metals), and 29 (Machinery and equipment, n.e.c.). Sivas exhibits a significant presence in sectors 1 (Agriculture, hunting, and related service activities), 24 (Chemicals and chemical products), and 29 (Machinery and equipment, n.e.c.). Yozgat's primary imports consistently include sectors 1 (Agriculture, hunting, and related service activities), 17 (Textiles and textile products), 18 (Manufacture of wearing apparel; dressing and dyeing of fur), and 29 (Machinery and equipment n.e.c). This highlights the province’s import trends and sector-specific dependencies within the TR72 Region.

Table 11. Top 5 Products Imported by Provinces in the TR72 Region

Year	Kayseri	Sivas	Yozgat
2013	1, 17, 24, 27, 29	1, 24, 29, 35 ,51	17, 18, 23, 29, 33
2014	1, 24, 27, 29, 35	1, 24, 29, 34 ,35	1, 17, 18, 29, 33
2015		1, 24, 29, 33, 35	1 ,17, 26, 27, 29
2016		1, 24, 29, 32, 35	1, 17, 26, 29, 33
2017		1, 24, 29, 32, 33	1, 15, 17, 29, 32
2018	1,24, 27, 29, 35	1, 24, 28, 29, 33	1, 17, 29, 31, 32
2019	1,17, 24, 27, 29		1, 17 ,23, 29, 36
2020	1, 24, 27, 29, 31		1, 17, 25, 26, 29
2021		24, 27, 28, 29, 33	1, 15, 27, 29, 51
2022	1, 24, 27, 29, 31		1, 17, 25, 26, 29
2023		1, 24, 25, 27, 29	1, 17, 18, 26, 29

5. METHODOLOGY

This study employs the Grubel-Lloyd index to evaluate the level of intra-industry trade (IIT) both across and within the TR72 region. The primary, though not sole, justification for this methodological choice lies in its widespread application in the existing literature. The Grubel-Lloyd index is a well-established measure in IIT analysis, designed to quantify the degree of similarity between a country's or region’s imports and exports within a specific industry.

This method expresses IIT as follows, where X_i represents the export value and M_i represents the import value (Grubel & Lloyd 1975: 21):

$$B_i = \frac{\sum_i^n [(X_i+M_i)-(X_i-M_i)]}{\sum_i^n (X_i+M_i)} \quad \text{or} \quad B_i = 1 - \frac{|X_i-M_i|}{X_i+M_i} \quad (1)$$

In formula 1, the absolute difference between exports and imports $|X_i - M_i|$ is divided by the sum of exports and imports $X_i + M_i$. This ratio is then subtracted from one, yielding a value that ranges between 0 and 1. An index value of 0 indicates that all trade in the sector is inter-industry, which means the country or region exports goods it does not import within the same industry. Conversely, a value of 1 reflects pure intra-industry trade (IIT), where exports and imports occur within the same industry. For a more nuanced analysis of IIT, the approach proposed by Abd-el-Rahman (1991) can be employed; however, this method requires more granular trade data, particularly concerning the quantities of goods traded. Such detailed data are typically available at the 3-digit or 5-digit classification level. Given that the present analysis is based on data aggregated at the 2-digit level, the application of the Abd-el-Rahman methodology is not feasible in this context.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TR72

In Table 12, the IIT structure in the TR72 Region is presented according to factor intensity. It is possible to classify manufacturing industry sectors according to their factor intensity under the headings of Raw Material-intensive, Scale-intensive, Labor-intensive, and Differentiated and Science-based industries, as per ISIC Rev. 3 (see Appendix).

None of the categories demonstrated a consistent presence of Intra-industry trade for the entire period. The analysis of the TR72 Region's factor intensity at the industry level, from 2013 to 2023, as shown in Table 12, reveals notable trends across industries that can be categorized as raw material-intensive, scale-intensive, labor-intensive, and differentiated. We have marked with an asterisk (*) the sectors that exhibited an IIT presence during the analyzed period. Key examples include:

- Within the differentiated and science-based industries, a consistent IIT is observed with an index consistently above 0.50, especially after 2018, for the sectors 21, 27, and 34.
- Despite varying index values within labor-intensive industries, sector 19 showed a fluctuating, but good level of IIT across several years. Generally, the region doesn't exhibit a high level of specialization across the sectors participating in this category.
- For scale-intensive industries, high index values suggest significant IIT, which is likely to be the case for many of the sectors included in this category. Some of them (21 and 25) showed a stable and high IIT across the period. The 25 industry experienced an increase in exports and a decrease in imports during the COVID-19 pandemic (from 2019 to 2021), resulting in a transformation from a sector with a high level of Intra-industry trade to one with significant inter-industry trade. For the other sectors, there is no stable trend.
- For the sectors part of the raw material-intensive industries category, no IIT presence was observed, except for sector 26, which overall showed a stable IIT presence across the period.

Table 12: IIT Structure of TR72 Region by Factor Intensity

Factor Intensity	Sector	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Raw material-intensive industries	15	0,28	0,39	0,54*	0,41	0,50*	0,34	0,49	0,45	0,46	0,69*	0,39
	16	na	na	na	Kayseri	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
	20	0,70*	0,33	0,45	0,40	0,37	0,29	0,18	0,13	0,11	0,16	0,11
	23	0,15	0,24	0,07	0,28	0,16	0,14	0,17	0,09	0,22	0,90*	0,74*
	26	0,61*	0,57*	0,81*	0,52*	0,44	0,42	0,51*	0,62*	0,64*	0,55*	0,81*
Avg.		0,44	0,38	0,47	0,40	0,37	0,30	0,34	0,32	0,36	0,58*	0,51*
Scale-intensive industries	21	0,36	0,37	0,68*	0,75*	0,69*	0,67*	0,80*	0,88*	0,98*	0,87*	0,86*
	22	0,67*	0,51*	0,44	0,38	0,51*	0,56*	0,41	0,49	0,53*	0,34	0,21
	24	0,12	0,13	0,16	0,20	0,25	0,35	0,42	0,40	0,24	0,29	0,27
	25	0,72*	0,72*	0,69*	0,68*	0,71*	0,55*	0,47	0,43	0,39	0,53*	0,63*
	27	0,21	0,28	0,26	0,25	0,28	0,57*	0,60*	0,57*	0,74*	0,82*	0,59*
	34	0,39	0,22	0,19	0,21	0,61*	0,97*	0,60*	0,42	0,36	0,38	0,64*
Avg.		0,36	0,32	0,35	0,37	0,44	0,53*	0,61*	0,59*	0,50*	0,49	0,50*
Labor-intensive industries	17	0,37	0,34	0,29	0,28	0,38	0,28	0,28	0,24	0,21	0,35	0,33
	18	0,31	0,40	0,04	0,12	0,21	0,22	0,07	0,01	0,09	0,05	0,26
	19	0,42	0,59*	0,69*	0,21	0,53*	0,04	0,09	0,09	0,35	0,64*	0,69*
	28	0,18	0,17	0,20	0,27	0,26	0,17	0,14	0,13	0,13	0,10	0,12
	36	0,27	0,17	0,19	0,05	0,03	0,05	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03
Avg.		0,31	0,33	0,28	0,19	0,28	0,15	0,12	0,10	0,16	0,23	0,29
Differentiated and science-based industries	29	0,81*	0,70*	0,70*	0,61*	0,56*	0,48	0,43	0,51*	0,56*	0,53*	0,55*
	30	0,18	0,24	0,19	0,20	0,29	0,12	0,50	0,49	0,15	0,10	0,74*
	31	0,24	0,35	0,41	0,39	0,46	0,29	0,25	0,33	0,35	0,22	0,26
	32	0,27	0,08	0,05	0,00	0,01	0,10	0,11	0,07	0,08	0,05	0,07
	33	0,83*	0,45	0,46	0,50*	0,39	0,71*	0,42	0,68*	0,75*	0,86*	0,65*
Avg.		0,47	0,36	0,36	0,34	0,34	0,34	0,34	0,42	0,38	0,35	0,45

Table 13 illustrates the IIT structure of Kayseri across various sectors categorized by factor intensity from 2013 to 2023. As for the overall region, Kayseri didn't sustainably register the presence of IIT during the entire considered period. Indeed, the situation is different at the level of each industry. The sectors that have registered the presence of IIT are listed as follows:

- Within the differentiated and science-based industries category, sector 29 shows the presence of intra-industry trade across the considered period. Additionally, Sector 33 has recently demonstrated a weak presence of IIT.
- A significant level of IIT was not observed within the labor-intensive industries category, except for sector 19, for some years.
- Regarding scale-intensive industries, the 21, 25, and 27 sectors exhibited the presence of IIT, albeit fluctuating.
- Related to raw material-intensive industries, industry 26 consistently demonstrates substantial Intra-industry trading activities over the years.

In 2013, Kayseri started with the presence of IIT in the following sectors: 20, 26, 22, 25, 29, and 33. At the end of the considered period, Kayseri exhibited the presence of IIT in the 23, 26, 21, 25, 27, 19, 29, and 30. Only industries 26, 25, and 29 maintained diversification and specialization over the entire period, with IIT values higher than 0,5.

Table 13: IIT Structure of Kayseri province by Factor Intensity

Factor Intensity	Sector	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
Raw n	15	0,34	0,49	0,69*	0,57*	0,64*	0,44	0,66*	0,61*	0,48	0,77*	0,41	
	16	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Raw material-intensive industries	26	0,56*	0,59*	0,02,84*	0,04,51*	0,03,51*	0,02,42	0,00,56	0,02,60	0,05,68	0,13,56	0,09,77	0,27,41
	16	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Scale-intensive industries	21	0,36	0,29,37	0,09,68*	0,10,73*	0,96,65*	0,72*,0,67*	0,20,0,80	0,07,0,87	0,14,0,98	na,0,87	0,00,0,80	na,0,21
	22	na	na	na	0,01	na	0,34	0,07	0,11	na	0,00	na	
	23	na	na	na	0,01	na	0,34	0,07	0,11	na	0,00	na	
	24	0,12	0,83,14	0,40,16	0,29,21	0,09,21	0,12,0,31	0,34,0,38	0,16,0,26	0,28,0,40	0,27,0,20	0,27,0,27	
	25	0,72*	0,72*	0,69*	0,68*	0,72*	0,53*	0,47	0,40	0,38	0,50*	0,53*	
Labor-intensive industries	27	0,21	0,28	0,26	0,25	0,28	0,57*	0,60*	0,58*	0,74*	0,83*	0,59*	
	34	0,36	0,09	0,11	0,18	0,57*	0,96*	0,27	0,19	0,22	0,23	0,48	
	35	0,38	0,01	0,01	0,19	0,00	0,01	0,58*	0,65*	0,22	0,20	0,22	
Avg.		0,40	0,30	0,34	0,37	0,42	0,52*	0,50*	0,50	0,47	0,46	0,45	
Differentiated and science-based industries	17	0,36	0,33	0,28	0,26	0,35	0,25	0,25	0,21	0,21	0,28	0,28	
	18	0,20	0,12	0,01	0,17	0,05	0,03	0,01	0,00	0,10	0,06	0,09	
	19	0,48	0,61*	0,72*	0,36	0,78*	0,02	0,12	0,10	0,29	0,50*	0,71*	
	28	0,19	0,16	0,19	0,27	0,25	0,15	0,11	0,10	0,11	0,09	0,10	
	36	0,27	0,17	0,19	0,05	0,03	0,05	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,02	
Avg.		0,30	0,28	0,28	0,22	0,29	0,10	0,10	0,09	0,15	0,19	0,24	
Differentiated and science-based industries	29	0,81*	0,70*	0,70*	0,58*	0,54*	0,46	0,42	0,50*	0,55*	0,53*	0,77*	
	30	0,18	0,25	0,20	0,20	0,30	0,13	0,73*	0,51*	0,15	0,09	0,76*	
	31	0,23	0,34	0,41	0,38	0,44	0,27	0,24	0,33	0,35	0,22	0,24	
	32	0,31	0,05	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,07	0,11	0,07	0,08	0,03	0,07	
	33	0,73*	0,30	0,34	0,42	0,21	0,58*	0,39	0,57*	0,57*	0,56*	0,40	
Avg.		0,45	0,33	0,34	0,32	0,30	0,30	0,38	0,40	0,34	0,29	0,45	

Table 14 presents the IIT structure of Sivas categorized by factor intensity from 2013 to 2023. Once again, none of the categories show intra-industry levels, which means overall in Sivas, there is no good integration with the global market. According to the findings:

- Sectors part of the scale-intensive industries, such as 21 and 24, highlight the presence of notable IIT activities
- Similarly, within the labor-intensive category, sectors like 17 and 28 demonstrated consistency in IIT levels, suggesting good levels of integration with the global market.
- Additionally, for differentiated and science-based industries, Sivas exhibited dynamic trade patterns, reflecting the presence of diversification, particularly within the 29 and 33 sectors.

In 2013, Sivas started with levels of IIT in the following sectors: 26, 25, 17, and 29. At the end of the considered period, Sivas exhibited the presence of IIT in the 21, 24, 35, 19, 28, 29, 31, and 33. Just sector 29, which encompasses Machinery and equipment n.e.c., has survived and maintained diversification and specialization over the entire period, with IIT levels superior to 0.5.

Table 14: IIT Structure of Sivas by Factor Intensity

Avg.		0,53*	0,25	0,22	0,36	0,43	0,29	0,11	0,19	0,4	0,2	0,38	
Scale-intensive industries	21	0,04	0,28	0,14	0,15	0,31	0,04	0,09	0,78*	0,56*	0,57*	0,58*	
	22	0,24	0,29	0,50*	0,88*	na	na	0,36	na	0,45	0,19	0,44	
	24	0,07	0,03	0,05	0,16	0,63*	0,99*	0,47	0,74*	0,57*	0,86*	0,55*	
Factor Intensity		Sector	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Raw material-intensive industries	15	0,02	0,14	0,19	0,26	0,33	0,46	0,13	0,05	0,76*	0,66*	0,34	
	16	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
	20	na	na	0,58*	0,85*	na	0,12	0,21	na	0,01	0,00	0,01	
	23	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Labor-intensive	12	0,50*	0,92*	0,03	0,10	0,09	0,03	0,09	0,12	0,24	0,92*	0,07	
	26	0,50*	0,92*	0,03	0,10	0,09	0,03	0,09	0,12	0,24	0,92*	0,07	
Avg.		21	0,26	0,53*	0,27	0,40	0,21	0,20	0,14	0,09	0,34	0,79*	0,14
Scale-intensive industries	22	0,72*	0,71*	0,301	0,53*	na	0,04	0,341	0,06	na	0,03	0,66*	0,44
	22	0,59*	na	na	na	0,57	0,38	0,07	na	0,16	0,23	0,21	
	32	0,98*	0,115	0,3519	0,0711	0,0417	0,0301	0,180*	0,37*	0,1671	0,0624	0,2059*	
	25	0,93*	0,91*	0,78*	0,99*	0,49	0,22	0,85*	0,28	0,58*	0,89*	0,37	
Differentiated and science-based industries	27	0,59*	0,76*	0,20	0,00	0,39	0,02	0,07	0,26	0,40	0,22	0,33	
	34	na	na	0,44	0,01	0,02	0,11	0,00	na	na	0,24	0,13	
	35	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0,025	na	0,40	
Avg.		33	0,76*	0,36	0,23	0,16	0,24	0,16	0,26	0,21	0,27	0,32	0,32
Avg.		33	0,47	0,26	0,96*	0,48	0,69*	0,88*	0,46	0,99*	0,74*	0,39	0,51*
Avg.			0,26	0,25	0,61*	0,46	0,31	0,62*	0,28	0,41	0,35	0,43	0,45

Table 15 illustrates the IIT structure of Yozgat’s foreign trade by factor intensity, which, unlike the other provinces, presents evident instability in terms of IIT values across most sectors, except for a few. For instance:

- Among the sectors part of the Raw material-intensive industries, none of the sectors showed stable patterns of IIT.
- The situation for the sectors part of the Scale-intensive industries is quite similar to the situation for raw-material-intensive industries. Sector 24 showed stability in the IIT pattern starting from 2017, with an interruption during the most intense year of the COVID-19 pandemic, 2019.
- Regarding the sectors within the Labor-intensive industries category, none of the industries exhibited stable IIT patterns, indicating that one-way trade exists within this category.
- For the Differentiated and Science-based Industries category, only the 29th industry had exhibited significant IIT in several years.

Table 15: IIT Structure of Yozgat’s Exports by Factor Intensity

Labor-intensive industries	17	0,83*	0,12	0,13	0,16	0,12	0,24	0,15	0,09	0,92*	0,81*	0,11
	18	0,68*	0,93*	0,07	0,08	0,62*	0,82*	0,24	0,13	0,03	0,04	0,44
	19	na	0,89*	0,09	na	0,28	0,02	na	0,25	0,29	0,11	0,33
	28	0,01	0,20	0,99*	0,56*	0,31	0,93*	0,90*	0,16	0,11	0,79*	0,58*
	36	0,60*	0,91*	0,83*	0,85*	0,97*	0,83*	0,44	0,36	0,05	0,14	0,66*
	Avg.	0,53*	0,61*	0,42	0,33	0,46	0,57*	0,35	0,20	0,28	0,38	0,42
Differentiated and science-based industries	29	0,52*	0,06	0,36	0,22	0,03	0,18	0,54*	0,88*	0,79*	0,87*	0,55*
	30	0,50*	na	na	na	na	na	na	0,19	na	na	na
	31	0,47	0,22	0,49	0,10	0,02	0,08	0,11	0,16	0,59*	0,26	0,26
	32	0,02	0,20	0,99*	na	0,66*	0,18	na	na	0,91*	0,71*	0,01
	33	0,66*	0,49	0,89*	0,31	0,85*	0,80*	0,52*	0,10	0,10	0,76*	0,15
	Avg.	0,43	0,24	0,68*	0,16	0,39	0,31	0,29	0,33	0,60*	0,65*	0,24

When comparing the results of the three provinces, Kayseri once again stands out. Kayseri’s IIT is characterized by stability and consistency in several sectors, particularly within raw-material, differentiated,

and science-based categories, as well as scale-intensive ones. This pattern indicates a strong level of integration into global markets, supported by a stable export structure. Sivas exhibits a relatively balanced intra-industry trade (IIT) profile across various industries. The presence of IIT in both labor-intensive and differentiated industries suggests a degree of diversification and specialization within the province’s industrial structure. In contrast, Yozgat displays a less stable IIT pattern, with few, if any, sectors showing consistent intra-industry trade activity. This inconsistency suggests a comparatively less developed industrial base, particularly when compared to Kayseri and Sivas.

While Kayseri exhibits consistent IIT patterns across several sectors, indicating a robust and diversified industrial base, Sivas and Yozgat lack the same level of stability, suggesting a need for further industrial development and diversification to achieve similar integration levels as Kayseri.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Intra-industry trade (IIT) serves as a key indicator of regional economic development and competitiveness in foreign exchange. The analysis of IIT in the TR72 region reveals a notable degree of specialization and reciprocal trade in similar goods, particularly in Kayseri, which demonstrates strong integration into global value chains.

The moderate level of intra-industry trade (IIT) in Kayseri reflects a strong specialization in the production of differentiated goods within similar sectors, highlighting the presence of a well-developed and diversified industrial base. This specialization enhances the province's economic resilience and competitiveness in both domestic and international markets.

Additionally, the Kayseri Free Trade Zone plays a significant role in supporting the region's trade structure. As one of Kayseri's top five export contributors, the Kayseri Free Trade Zone strengthens export and import activities by offering incentives such as tax advantages, efficient customs procedures, and supportive infrastructure. These benefits promote business development, attract foreign investment, and foster international trade partnerships, further reinforcing Kayseri's position in global trade.

For Sivas and Yozgat to enhance their performance in this area, it is crucial to strengthen industrial infrastructure and implement targeted support mechanisms for foreign trade. In this regard, the special incentives allocated to the Nuri Demirağ Organized Industrial Zone in Sivas may play a constructive role in boosting the province's future IIT potential.

This study provides a foundation for understanding why, in a region like TR72, where provinces share similar structural characteristics, significant differences in business opportunities and trade development still emerge. To deepen the understanding of intra-industry trade (IIT) dynamics in the region, future research should consider the following areas:

1. Examine the industrial structure and specialization within TR72: Identify the key industries driving IIT in each province and analyze patterns of specialization and comparative advantage to understand the region's industrial dynamics better.
2. Differentiate between vertical and horizontal IIT: To capture the complexity of IIT, further analysis should distinguish between vertical (quality-differentiated) and horizontal (similar-quality) trade. This requires access to more detailed data, ideally at the 5-digit level.
3. Conduct firm-level analysis: Gathering data from individual firms through case studies or surveys can shed light on the strategies, motivations, and competitive behaviors of firms engaged in IIT. This micro-level perspective can reveal essential factors influencing decision-making and competitiveness.

By exploring these areas, future research can offer deeper insights into the mechanisms shaping IIT in TR72, supporting more effective policymaking and strategic planning aimed at fostering regional economic development.

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APPENDIX

ISIC Rev. 3 2-digit Classification Based on Technological Intensity

Raw material-intensive industries	
15	Food products and beverages
16	Tobacco products
20	Wood and cork products (excluding furniture)
23	Coke, refined petroleum products and nuclear fuels
26	And other nonmetallic mineral products
Scale-intensive industries	
21	Paper and paper products
22	Printing and publishing; records, tapes, etc.
24	Chemicals and chemical products
25	Rubber and plastic products
27	Basic metals
34	Motor vehicles and trailers

35	Other transport equipment
Labor-intensive industries	
17	Textiles
18	Clothing
19	Tanned leather, luggage, handbags, saddlery, and footwear
28	Fabricated metal products (except machinery and equipment)
36	Furniture and other products not elsewhere classified (n.e.c)
Differentiated and science-based industries	
29	Machinery and equipment n.e.c.
30	Office accounting and computing machinery
31	Electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c.
32	Radio, Television, and communication equipment and apparatus
33	Medical instruments, precision, and optical instruments and watches